

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Lin**FIRST NAME:** Yi Lung**PROGRAM CODE:** DILT**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 18%

The author used the following software: Microsoft 365 Personal

QUIZ FOR COURSE PERIOD 6

1. Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021). Critical thinking is vital in research, and it helps to:

Identify the author's name, title, and publisher.

Exempt standards and evaluating sources.

Disregard to alternative viewpoints.

Effectively analyze information and form a judgment.¹

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 9.

2. Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021). How to avoid plagiarism? Indicate your understanding.

Writer disregards the creditability of the author.

Writer failed to mention the source.

Writer was unable to cite.

Writer must properly cite the author or the source provided for the information he uses.²

3. Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021). In academic writing, what does a style guide mean?

It is a rule for the writing.

It is a formatting rule.

It is a rule for layouts of documents.

It is a tool for ensuring consistency and accuracy in the content of your writing.³

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 34.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 41.

4. Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021). Which one belongs to the Turabian parenthetical citations?

(Author's Last Name Year of Publication, XX).⁴ (Tork 2020, 88)

(Author's Last Name and a page number). (Matthew 44).

(Author's Last Name, year of publication, and page number). (Adam, 2010, p. 4).

(Author. Title. Journal. Year; Volume(Issue): Page Number). (Eddie M. Heat regulator. MedJournal. 2005;(8):10-20.

5. Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021). Is Turabian Style entirely the same as the Chicago Manual of Style?

Yes, completely the same.

No, entirely not the same.

I am not that sure.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers. Ninth Edition* (Chicago, London: University of Chicago Press., 2018). 18.

There are some differences. Turabian is a lessened version for students writing research papers. Chicago Manual of Style is for professionals either engaged in publishing or in demand for formatting books and research papers.⁵

6. Turabian et al. (2018). “Ibid” is an acronym of the Latin “ibidem,” meaning “in the same place.” Under what circumstances you cannot use *ibid* for footnote citation?

When too many *ibid* already appeared.

Chicago Style Citation Guide permits the use of *ibid* without limitation.

Avoid using *ibid* when there is a new citation cited.⁶

Turabian did not prohibit the use of *ibid*.

7. Bloomberg and Volpe (2019). Why literature review is essential to a researcher?

It is part of an academic essay.

It is a research paper.

It is an annotated bibliography.

⁵ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 44, 50.

⁶ Turabian et al., 16.

It is a tool for advanced practice directly related to the Researcher's aim and purpose. The Researcher can gather past and present information and help develop new questions from his findings.⁷

8. Bloomberg and Volpe (2019). Qualitative research is complex without numbers. What is the role of a qualitative researcher?

He is a data collector.

He is a data analyst.

He is a storyteller.

He attempts to describe the meaning of the findings from research participants, and to achieve this goal, data are collected directly from the participants.⁸

9. Bloomberg and Volpe (2019). What factors a researcher must consider in selecting a research approach?

The research problem.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Maria Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End. Fourth Edition* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 8.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 7.

The literature review.

The study's audience.

The research problem, the Researcher's experience, knowledge from the literature review, and the study's audience.⁹

10. Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021). The researchers can use quotations in their work, but to prove their research, they consider specific limitations.

Researchers can choose the right quotes and integrate them.

Qualitative research studies are evidence and are unlimited.

Researcher uses a quote in research and changes the paraphrasing.

Use the quotation when there is vital language that can support the meaning well and help persuade the readers.¹⁰

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 7-8.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 36.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition. Los Angeles: SAGA Publications, Inc., 2019.

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Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colombo, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth Edition. Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.